

Emotion Recognition through Facial Expression Using CNN

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Abstract- In recent past years, facial emotion recognition has been widely used in many applications and fields such as security, banking, marketing, and even in daily life applications. People usually refer to their mood or psychological states through emotions. There are many attempts has been focused on facial emotion recognition using deep learning techniques such as convolutional neural network (CNN). In this paper, propose a novel model to detect the changes of emotions of people, based on CNN with some popular libraries such as TensorFlow and Keras. The experimental results of the proposed model show the model performance in term of accuracy achieved 99.59%.

Keywords- Facial Expressions, Convolution Neural Network, Google Colab, TensorFlow, Keras.

1 INTRODUCTION

Over the past decades, studies and researches have focused on creating methods that facilitate recognition and analysis of human emotions. It was noted that recognizing emotions had a significant role in developing and improving many areas. The face is considered the window for recognizing an individual's personality, emotions, and thoughts, and it is the most distinctive visual feature of an individual. Thus, it plays an essential role in knowing and perceiving emotions and communication between humans, as facial expressions are the most non-verbal communication in the interaction between humans. Mehrabian mentioned in [1] that facial expressions represent the message of the speaker by 55%, while the verbal components represent 7% and the vocal components only 38%. Ekman and others have defined the basic facial expressions in six categories (happiness, sadness, fear, disgust, anger, and surprise) regardless of race or nationality [2].

Empathy can be defined as a psychological process that includes understanding another person through their emotions [3]. It is a physiological and mental state associated with a set of thoughts and emotions. If people understand the emotions of a person in distress, they can help that person and interact with him. The person's emotions also have a large role in making his decisions. In a study conducted by the neuroscientist Antonio Damasio, he stated that people who have damages to the emotion-related brain part have great difficulty in making decisions [4].

One of the main challenges of facial expression recognition algorithms is to identify parameters that are independent of human face identity. Indeed, facial expressions can be inconsistent in shape and texture. Various studies have been proposed to automatically recognize facial expressions. Some of these methods use shape constraints [6] Or use a statistical model that collects shape and texture information to extract facial expressions along with machine learning approaches to identify facial expressions [7]. On the other hand, some methods use appearance-based techniques such as Gabor

features and LBP binary patterns to extract facial features and then apply an expression recognition classification system. Recognizing facial expressions is the primary task of intelligent systems based on the interaction between Computer and Human (HCI) as it had a great interest in the scientific community. There are many applications in

computers that have been used to recognize emotions through facial expressions. Machine learning algorithms have proven their ability to classify emotions based on the extracted features. The process of detecting emotions includes the following steps, in general figure1 [8].

Figure 1: Process of detecting emotion

2 FACIAL EXPRESSION BACKGROUND:

Facial expressions can be defined physiologically as muscle activity in the face. The face consists of about 20 muscles that move to express the person's emotions.

Ekman released the Facial Action Coding System (FACS) in 1978 [6]. FACS has been built based on examining the relation between facial muscle contractions and the changes caused by them. Muscle contractions are known as action units (AU) in this framework. The analysis of expression in FACS is based on the analysis of expression in the work units. The facial expressions have 46 AUs, and the head and eye

Figure 1: Action Units corresponding to different movements in face [12]

Table 1: Prototypical AUs observed in each basic and compound emotion category [13]

Category	AUs	Category	AUs
Happy	12, 25	Sadly disgusted	4, 10
Sad	4, 15	Fearfully angry	4, 20, 25
Angry	4, 7, 24	Fearfully surprised	1, 2, 5, 20, 25
Fearful	1, 4, 20, 25	Fearfully disgusted	1, 4, 10, 20, 25
Surprised	1, 2, 25, 26	Angrily surprised	4, 25, 26
Disgusted	9, 10, 17	Disgusted Surprised	1, 2, 5, 10
Happily sad	4, 6, 12, 25	Happily fearful	1, 2, 12, 25, 26
Happily surprised	1, 2, 12, 25	Angrily disgusted	4, 10, 17
Happily Disgusted	10, 12, 25	Aweed	1, 2, 5, 25
Sadly Angry	4, 7, 15	Appalled	4, 9, 10
Sadly surprised	1, 4, 25, 26	Hatred	4, 7, 10
Sadly fearful	1, 4, 15, 25		

3 FACIAL EXPRESSION RECOGNITION (FER) APPROACHES :

Modern approaches are based on deep learning algorithms . Deep learning has demonstrated excellent efficiency in many machine learning assignments, including target identification, target detection, and classification. For FER, in environments with different elements, such as blockage and lighting, deep learning techniques have significantly reduced reliance on pre-processing and feature extraction and are more robust from machine learning techniques. It can accommodate vast quantities of data as well. It, therefore, outperforms the classical approaches significantly [9]. Deep learning in FER goes through three main steps: preprocessing, deep feature learning, and deep feature classification is also given in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Process Diagrams of the deep FER System

A-Preprocessing:

Variations that are incidental to facial expressions, such as various backgrounds, illuminations and head poses, are very common in unregulated scenarios. Therefore, prior to training the deep neural network , pre-processing is required to align and normalize the visual semantic information conveyed by the face[9].Figure4.

- **Face alignment:** is an important and traditional step in many FER approaches.

- **data augmentation:** Deep neural networks need comprehensive training data to make the recognition task more general. Most publicly available FER databases do not contain sufficient images. Therefore, data augmentation is a significant step for deep FER.
- **Illumination normalization:** Variations in illumination and head poses cause significant image changes and thus impair the FER's output. Several illumination normalization algorithms are frequently used, such as isotropic diffusion-based normalization (IS), normalization based on discrete cosine transform (DCT) and the most famous of which is Viola-Jones (V&J).Figure 5.
- **Pose normalization:** It is another common and intractable issue in unconstrained settings is significant pose variation. Some experiments have used techniques of pose normalization to create 6 FERR frontal facial views.

Figure 4: The general pipeline of deep facial expression recognition systems .

Figure5: Grayscale 2D images of a face (a) before and (b) after normalization.

B- Feature extraction and Facial expression classification:

Modern approaches attempt to capture high-level features in the feature extraction stage through hierarchical structures with various transformations and non-linear representations. Typical structures of deep neural networks are shown in Figure 21. Modern Approaches differ from traditional methods in which the feature extraction step and the feature classification step are separated independently. Modern Approaches for FER is implemented comprehensively. It adds a loss layer at the end of the network to regulate the back-propagation error, then the prediction probability of each sample can be taken out directly from the network [9].

There are many algorithms of the modern approach. The most common methods used like CNN, DBN will be mentioned.

4 CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORKS (CNNs)

Convolution neural network is a form of feedforward neural network which can extract features from data with convolution structures. CNN's architecture is influenced by visual perception. Unlike conventional methods of extraction of features [14], CNN does not need to manually extract features. A biological neuron corresponds to an artificial neuron; CNN kernels represent multiple receptors which can react to different features and activation functions simulate the role of transmitting to the next neuron neural electric signals reaching a certain threshold. The kernels of the CNN reflect various receptors, capable of responding to many features. Loss functions and optimizers are invented to tell the whole CNN system and learn what we expected. CNN is characterized by local communication, as every neuron is no longer connected to all neurons from the previous layer, the dimensions of the samples are reduced, the parameters are reduced by sharing the weight where the group of connections can share the same weight. A pooling layer uses the idea of a local image correlation that goal to the down-sample an image which can minimize the amount of data while preserving useful information. The number of parameters can also be reduced by eliminating trivial features [16] figure 6.

Figure 6: CNN Architecture

four components are usually required to construct a CNN model. Convolution is a crucial step in the extraction of features. Convolution outputs can be called feature maps. When we set a convolution kernel of a certain size, we lose information at the edge. Padding is then added to raise the input with a zero value, which can indirectly change size. Furthermore, phase is used to regulate the density of convolving. The bigger the move, the lower the density. Feature maps consist of a large number of features that are vulnerable to overfitting problems after convolution [17]. As a consequence, pooling [18] (sampling down), like max pooling and average pooling, is proposed to prevent redundancy figure 7.

Figure 7: Procedure of a two-dimensional CNN

4.1 FER based on Convolutional Neural Networks

A CNN consists of an input layer, several hidden layers, and an output layer. The pooling layers, multiple convolutional layers, normalization layers, and fully connected layers are all of the hidden layers. In Figure 8, a CNN has 5 layers [93]. In CNN-based FER the image is convolved to create a feature map using a filter collection in the convolution layers. Each feature map is then combined into fully connected networks, and the SoftMax algorithm recognizes the facial expression as belonging to a specific class.

figure 9. FER may also be split into two categories, depending on a frame or video images. First, static (frame-based) FER relies solely on static facial features, derived from handcrafted extraction features from selected image sequence expression frames. Second, FER uses dynamic (video-based) features to capture expression dynamics in sequences of facial expression [17].

Figure 8: Architecture of a 5-layered CNN [93]

Figure 9 Architecture of CNN classifier

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Deep Convolutionary Neural Networks for Facial Expression Recognition were proposed in paper [21]. It was noted that two datasets test the efficacy of the proposed CNN model: the JAFFE data base and the Cohn-Kanade database. In the first assessment, the JAFFE database and images with 256 x 256 resolution pixels were used. The second evaluation used the Cohn-Kanade database and the images with a 640 x 490 or 640 x 480 resolution pixel. The methods used in this paper:

- CNNs receive image inputs.
- The CNN model is implemented in nine layers.
- The size of the image was changed to 16x16, for 30 epochs, the suggested model was trained.

However, the results summarized that the expression recognition rate respectively 96.10 %.

- Improved facial expression recognition based on the DWT feature of Deep CNN was proposed in the paper [22]. In this paper, the CK + database consists of 593 images from a total of 123 subjects with human face emotion based on a person's impression of each of the seven basic emotions, and the JAFFE face database consists of 213 greyscale images of 10 Japanese models. The methodology of this paper demonstrates that the facial expression recognition scheme is performed in four main steps: identification of facial parts, facial image optimization, facial feature extraction, and expression classification that Viola Jones uses to detect the face. Facial parts will improve facial image using CLAHE; Facial contour extraction using DWT; The extracted features are used to train CNN to categorize facial expressions. The accuracy of the expression recognition is 98.63 percent and 97.05 percent, respectively, in the JAFFE database and the CK + database.

- Deeper models have better facial and emotional classification results.

- The Light-CNN experiments nevertheless showed that a shallow CNN could also achieve good results in the wild for facial expression .

- merging feature sets does not improve accuracy.

The FER2013 dataset was used in more research, such as the paper [24] The FER2013 dataset consists of 48 * 48 pixel grayscale images of faces. The approach was based on cropping the central regions of the original images randomly and converting the cropped images horizontally. There are 3 CNN sub-nets in this model. The grids contain 8 to 10 layers and the features extracted by these subnets are grouped together by adding a fully connected layer at the end. And as an output layer for the entire network, the softmax layer is used. The model achieved accuracy 65.03%.

In [25] done identified the Recognition of learning-centered emotions using a convolutionary neural network. They used three databases, one is called RaFD consists of 1146 of basic emotions. The author collects the two databases and they belong to learner's emotions. Emotiv epic database (dbE) consists of 730 photographs, and Emotiv insight database (dbI) consists of 5560 labelling images. For their experiments in this paper, it is proposed to use convolutional neural networks (CNNs) so that students' emotions are recognized during their learning. The CNN consists of three max-pooling layers, and three convolutional layers, and three neural network layers. Convolutional layer consists of three elements data input, kernel, and output which is known as feature map. Pooling is a grouping function which by taking the maximum values, modifies the results obtained from the convolution layer. The last three fully connected neural networks layers are classification layers, they use Softmax function for classification. The resulted report shows that the data divided as 90% for training and 10% for testing. The CNN accuracy obtained with RaFD were 95%, with dbE were 88%. According to dbI the accuracy was 74%, it gets the lowest results comparing to the two databases because preprocessing didn't perform for this database.

The paper [26] proposed on personalized models for recognition of facial emotions through transfer learning. They used two emotionally labelled databases AffectNet and AMIGOS. This paper aims to produce a general facial emotion recognition (FER) model as called "one-fits-all". They proposed transfer learning approach, this approach means solving one problem and storing the gained knowledge to be applied later on different but related problem. First, they trained CNN using AlexNet algorithm over AffectNet database. Then, they used small data from AMIGOS dataset to perform fine-tuning (retraining the CNN model with new dataset) by exploiting the gained knowledge from previous step. The Greedy Sampling(GS) and Monte-Carlo Dropout Uncertainty Estimation (MCDUE) are suggested to reduce the number of samples in the fine-tuning step. In results, the suggested generalized transferred knowledge gives high recognition performance in generalized model and personal models.

5 CNN IMPLEMENTATION:

In this section, the structure of CNN and the pre-processing methods for FER2013 images will be discussed before they are inserted into CNN.

5.1 Dataset Collection:

The FER-2013 dataset includes 28,000 images labeled in the training set, 3,500 images labeled in the test set, and 3,500 images labeled in the output set. The dataset was created for every emotion and synonyms for emotions by collecting Google's image search results. Each image in FER-2013 is classified as one of seven emotions, including (0= anger, 1= disgust, 2= fear, 3= happiness, 4= sadness, 5= surprise and 6= neutral) figure 10 . Ian Goodfellow determined that this data set has approximately 65.5% human accuracy [30].

Figure 10: Example images from the FER2013 dataset

5.2 Tools used:

A- Google Colab environment

It is Python development environment, that run using Google cloud and provides free GPU, because training models on CPU takes a long time so using GPU is better than CPU. It allows us to write and execute our deep learning applications. Dealing with large datasets in Google Colab is easy because it offer uploading the dataset on Google drive and then map

it to Google Colab using "Mount Drive" button. In addition, it is suitable for machine learning. It provides a lot of popular libraries such as TensorFlow, Keras, PyTorch, and OpenCV libraries.

B- TensorFlow library

TensorFlow is open-source library used to implement deep learning and machine learning models. It is used for fast numerical computation also it uses computational graphs for data flow. The name TensorFlow means data flows through the graph, and each graph consists of nodes and each node represents mathematical operations. It's job is to transfer complex data to artificial neural network later for analysis [27]. Moreover, TensorFlow advantage is that it can be deploy in a variety of platforms such as Android. Some of important features are true portability that means it runs on CPU, GPU, mobile computing [28]. Also, language options it written in C++ and Python as we use in this project. TensorBoard is used as visualization tool with TensorFlow library. Many data types can be visualized using TensorBoard such as graphs, scales, images, histograms, and audio. Usually TensorBoard installed along with TensorFlow [29].

C- Keras library

Keras is another open-source library used for deep learning. It is high level neural network Application Programming Interface (API), it can be used alone or also used with TensorFlow library. One of its benefits is that it can run easily on both CPU and GPU. In addition, it allow us to easily build neural networks. About TensorFlow, Keras is usually used in top of Tensorflow library [29].

5.3 Pre-Processing:

Pre-processing was used in this model to improve its performance. In the FER2013 data, they have similar space requirements because faces are recorded automatically. Methods used in the proposed model first were to be resized to 48 x 48 pixels for analysis. Then a normalization of the images was done to change the range of pixel density values so that all the images shared a similar range of grayscale where the gradient image was normalized. Gray using 255.0 .

5.4 CNN Architecture:

The size of the input image for the form is (length x width x depth). For example, when you insert a 24 x 24-pixel colour image through a neural network. It will be the total input of the network $24 \times 24 \times 3$, where 3 refers to the RGB channels for a colour image. In this experiment, the image has a greyscale size of 48 x 48 pixels. Thus the total input for the first layer in the network will be $48 \times 48 \times 1$. Neurons in layers can only link to a small portion of the layer preceding it. For the output layer, its size will be $1 \times 1 \times N$, which represents the image in one vector of the class scores. In this experiment, $N = 7$ because it classifies seven emotions. The model consists of 22 layers, an input layer, an output layer, and 14 hidden layers. It is consisted of five convolution layers, five max-pooling layers, five BatchNormalization layers, four Dropout

layer, one Flatten layer, one fully connected layer, and a softmax layer for classifying results figure 11.

Figure 11: 2DCNN Proposed model Architecture.

5.5 Results

For training the data samples in this experiment, 50 epochs were used. The training accuracy improved while the loss decreased with each epoch. Table 2 shows the performance assessment, while figure11 shows a curve of accuracy and loss. Figure12 shows emotion recognition samples for images from outside the dataset.

Performance Parameters	Performance Metrics (%)
Training Loss	0.0434
Training Accuracy	0.9959
Validation Loss	0.2153
Validation Accuracy	0.9749
Test Accuracy	0.5846
Test Loss	2.4173

Table 2: Performance evaluation based on training and validation and Testing accuracy and loss.

Figure 12: Proposed model accuracy and loss.

Figure 12: Proposed Model test

CONCLUSION

This work presents an application of recognizing facial emotion based deep learning. The proposed architecture is convolutional neural network to recognize person's emotions. The aim of this system is to show the person's emotion shifting between some specific emotions categories: happiness, anger, sadness, fear, and normal. The system trained and tested using FER2013 dataset. The evaluation of the architecture show that the system can perfectly detect the facial emotion with accuracy of 99.95%.

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